

Dye Alcohol Interaction in Aprotic Media-Part II*: Kinetic Studies

Sadhan Kumar De** and Santi R. Palit

The kinetics of reaction between carbinol base of ethyl violet and alcohols in aprotic media to give the violet coloured salt has been studied spectrophotometrically. The rate of the first order reaction was calculated by the equation $k = (2.303/t) \log x_e/x_e - x$, where x is the optical density at time, t , and x_e is the optical density when equilibrium is attained; k , the overall rate constant was evaluated graphically from the slopes obtained by plotting $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time.

The results show that alcohol catalyses its own reaction—a fact which also has been confirmed by experiments with mixtures of alcohols, in which case cross-catalysis was found to take place. The first order rate constant is not directly proportional to the catalyst concentration as it is usually the case in catalysed reactions, but the ratio k/C increases linearly with C , the alcohol concentration. The results are expressible by an equation of the type, $k/C = k\alpha + k\beta C$, where $k\alpha$ and $k\beta$ are constants characteristic of the alcohol. Self-association of alcohol molecules is probably the reason for such abnormal behaviour. Values of $k\alpha$ obtained graphically from the intercept of the plot of k/C vs C may be taken as a rough measure of the strengths of the alcohols in aprotic media. $k\alpha$ follows the order, $CF_3CH_2OH > H(CF_2-CF_2)_2CH_2OH > H(CF_2-CF_2)_3-CH_2OH > CH_3C(NO_2)_2CH_2OH > CF_3COCF_3, H_2O$. This order does not run parallel with the acidities in water.

The equilibrium studies of the interaction between carbinol base of ethyl violet and alcohols in aprotic media were reported earlier¹.

The attainment of equilibrium on the addition of alcohols to the dye-base in benzene as represented below:

is a slow process. Its rate can be conveniently measured. And since such rate measurements in aprotic media have bearing on our knowledge of the kinetics of acid-base neutralisation and catalysis by acids (or bases), the kinetic studies were undertaken. The present paper reports the results of such kinetic studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvents used are benzene, toluene and xylene. The alcohols are C_3 -fluoroalcohol ($H-CF_2-CF_2-CH_2OH$), C_5 -fluoroalcohol ($H(CF_2-CF_2)_2(CH_2OH)$), C_7 -fluoroalcohol ($H(CF_2CF_2)_3CH_2OH$), trifluoroethanol (CF_3CH_2OH), 2, 2-dinitropropanol ($CH_3C(NO_2)_2CH_2OH$) and hexafluoroacetone hydrate (CF_3COCF_3, H_2O). The dye base is the carbinol base of ethyl violet. The preparation of dye base and various solutions have been described elsewhere^{1,2,3}.

* Part I: Equilibrium studies, see ref. 1.

** Present address: —Department of Applied Chemistry,

Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, W. Bengal.

1. S. K. De and S. R. Palit, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 395.
2. S. K. De and S. R. Palit, *Science and Culture*, 1966, 32, 543.

Before starting the actual experiment, the experimental solutions of both carbinol base and alcohols of desired strength were prepared from the stock solutions and were kept for about thirty minutes in a thermostat maintained at 35°. When the solutions attained the temperature of the bath, they were mixed with thorough shaking, the time of mixing was noted. Next the mixture was quickly transferred into a stoppered absorption cell (at 35°) and finally transferred in the cell compartment maintained at 35° ± 0.5°. The mixing of the solution and the transfer of the mixture to the cell compartment was finished in about two minutes and the first reading could be taken in about three minutes after the start of the experiment. Sufficient time was allowed for attaining the equilibrium before noting down the equilibrium reading. The spectrophotometric readings were taken at 605 mμ which is the absorption maximum of the coloured salt¹.

Two sets of kinetic experiments were done. In the first the carbinol base concentration was varied and the alcohol concentration was kept fixed and in the second the alcohol concentration was varied, the carbinol base concentration being fixed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rate constant has been calculated from the first order equation

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where x is the optical density reading at time t and x_e is the reading when equilibrium is attained. Time, t , is taken in minutes and k is the overall rate constant. The rate constants were evaluated graphically from the slopes obtained by plotting $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time.

When the concentration of carbinol base is varied and the alcohol concentration is kept fixed, we obtain parallel straight lines (Fig. 1).

FIG 1

Fig. 1. Plot of $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time at different concentrations of carbinol base in toluene. Concentration of C_6 -fluoroalcohol in all cases is 0.2157M.

	$C \times 10^6$ (M)
(1)	6.735
(2)	11.225

Thus the values of apparent velocity constant, k , are constant within experimental error (Table I).

TABLE—I

Velocity constants at different nasse concentrations

C_5 -Fluoroalcohol

$C \times 10^6$ (M)	(Results in Toluene)	$k \times 10$ (min. ⁻¹)
6.735		1.382
11.225		1.393

This shows that the velocities of reactions between carbinol base and different alcohols are independent of the carbinol base concentration; that is, the reactions are strictly of first order with respect to carbinol base.

But in the plottings of $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. t at various alcohol concentrations and fixed carbinol base concentration, we still obtain good straight line graphs for different alcohols, but they are no longer parallel to each other (Fig. 2). The values of k increase with the increase in alcohol concentration. Thus we arrive at the following

FIG 2

Fig.2. Plots of $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time at different concentrations of C_5 -fluoroalcohol in benzene medium. Concentration of carbinol base in all cases is 6.09×10^{-6} M

$C \times 10^2$ (M)

(1) 1.961

(2) 2.353

(3) 2.745

(4) 3.922

conclusions :

- (i) When $-\log(x_0 - x)$ is plotted against time, linear graphs are obtained under all conditions; that is, the course of the reaction is strictly unimolecular.
- (ii) The increase in rate constant with the increase in alcohol concentration indicates that the concentration term of alcohol occurs in the velocity expression to a higher power than it does in the stoichiometric equation.

Our first conclusion is in harmony with the kinetics of a reaction of the following type (where the concentration of alcohol is very high compared to that of carbinol base):

From the second conclusion we believe that the reaction may be catalysed by alcohols. Since the aprotic solvents take no part in protolytic equilibria, there are no ions corresponding to hydrogen ions, so that the reaction is catalysed by alcohol molecules. Therefore the reaction shows the characteristics of "general acid catalysis"⁴. Besides, the reaction fails to take place in the absence of the alcohol, thus showing that the alcohol may play the dual role of both reactant and catalyst. This fact has been further confirmed by our results with mixtures of alcohols where 'cross-catalysis'⁴ takes place. That is, when two alcohols are present together, each alcohol catalyse the reaction of the other. Thus we should expect a total reaction velocity greater than the sum of velocities for the two alcohols when present separately at the same concentration, that is, the value of ' Δ ' (described below) should be positive.

Let us suppose,

k_A, k_B = observed velocity constants for the two alcohols, A and B.

k_{AB} = observed velocity constant for the mixture and

$$\Delta = k_{AB} - (k_A + k_B)$$

The values of Δ for the alcohol pairs given in Table II are positive. In the pairs studied Δ varied from 75 to 115 per cent of $k_A + k_B$, which is indeed a remarkable mixture effect.

TABLE—II

Values of Δ for different alcohol pairs (Results in Benzene)

Alcohols	k_{AB} (min. ⁻¹)	$k_A + k_B$ (min. ⁻¹)	$\Delta = k_{AB} \cdot (k_A + k_B)$
Trifluoroethanol and C ₇ -Fluoroalcohol	0.3409	0.1589	0.1820
Trifluoroethanol and C ₃ -Fluoroalcohol	0.4422	0.2281	0.2141
C ₃ -Fluoroalcohol and C ₇ -Fluoroalcohol	0.3224	0.1842	0.1382

Variation of k/C with C

Our results show that the first order rate constant is not directly proportional to the catalyst concentration as it is usually the case in catalysed reactions, but the

4. R. P. Bell, "Acid-Base Catalysis", (Oxford), 1941.

ratio, k/C , increases with increase in C (Fig. 3). Similar results were obtained previously by Bhowmick and Palit⁵ while studying interaction between carbinol base of

Fig. 3. Plot of k/C vs. C for C_7 -fluoroalcohol in
(1) Benzene
(2) Xylene

crystal violet and various carboxylic acids and phenol in benzene medium. It was found that in most cases the ratio, k/C , decreases with increase in acid concentration, except for phenol and monochloroacetic acid. In the present case, however, the slope of k/C vs C plot is positive in all cases. Thus, our results may be expressed by an equation of the type,

$$k = k_{\alpha} C + k_{\beta} C^2$$

$$\text{or } k/C = k_{\alpha} + k_{\beta} C \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where k_{α} and k_{β} are constants for each alcohol. Brönsted and Bell⁶, while studying the reaction of diazoacetic ester catalysed by various acids in benzene, found that the value of the velocity constant increased with the increase in acid concentration and their results could be expressed by an expression similar to (2). They concluded that the association of carboxylic acid molecules was responsible for such increase in velocity constant.

It has been pointed out in our equilibrium studies¹ that alcohol molecules remain associated in aprotic solvents. And it is possible that the presence of dimeric forms along with other associated forms are responsible for the variation of velocity constant with alcohol concentration. For 2, 2-dinitropropanol, it has been found that k/C changes little with increase in alcohol concentration. Our kinetic results agree with the equilibrium results¹ where it has been found that 2, 2-dinitropropanol exists predominantly as the monomeric species and the self-association is small in this case.

Relation between acidities in water and k_{α} in benzene.

5. S. R. Bhowmick and S. R. Palit, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 1049.
6. J. N. Bronsted and R. P. Bell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2478.

TABLE—III
Values of k_{α} in different solvents

Alcohol	pKa in water ^{8,9}	k_{α}		
		Benzene	Toluene	Xylene
Trifluoroethanol	11.31	-0.66	-0.67	—
C ₅ -fluoroalcohol	11.34	0.145	—	—
C ₇ -fluoroalcohol	11.33	0.20	—	0.20
2, 2-dinitropropanol	—	1.60	—	—
Hexafluoroacetone hydrate	6.58	1450	—	—

From Table III it is evident that (i) values of k_{α} are nearly the same in benzene, toluene and xylene.

(ii) Values of k_{α} follow the order, Trifluoroethanol < C₅-Fluoroalcohol < C₇-Fluoroalcohol < 2, 2-dinitropropanol < Hexafluoroacetone hydrate.

(iii) Values of k_{α} do not always run parallel with the acidities in water. Both kinetic and equilibrium results show that owing to several complicating factors the strengths of alcohols in aprotic solvents do not follow the order as reported in water¹. It may be mentioned here that the pKa values of alcohols in water reported so far are not always reliable.⁷

Individual Rate Constants

Recently Bhowmick and Palit have developed an equation to determine the individual rate constants of dye-acid interaction⁵:

$$\log \frac{k}{K + (\text{Acid})^n} = \log k_{-1} + f \log (\text{Acid})$$

where $n = f - r$ (f stands for acid component for forward reaction and r , for reverse reaction). Thus the plot of $\log k/K + (\text{Acid})^n$ vs $\log (\text{Acid})$ should yield a straight line with slope equal to 'f' and intercept equal to $\log k_{-1}$.

The above relationship for dye-acid interaction has been found to hold good for dye-alcohol interaction too. Good linear $\log = \log$ plots have been obtained for all alcohols (Fig. 4). The results are summarised in Table-IV.

Fig. 4. Plots of $-\log k/K + (\text{Acid})^n$ vs. $\log (\text{Acid})$ for
(1) C₅-fluoroalcohol
(2) C₇-fluoroalcohol
(3) Trifluoroethanol
(4) 2, 2-dinitropropanol

TABLE—IV

Individual Rate Constants (Results in Benzene Medium)

Alcohol	log K*	log k_1	log k_{-1}	n*	f	r
C ₅ -fluoroalcohol	2.620	0.520	-2.1	2.0	2.07	0.07
C ₇ -fluoroalcohol	2.433	1.758	-0.675	1.58	2.50	0.92
Trifluoroethanol	1.767	1.617	-0.15	3.8	5.7	1.9
2, 2-dinitropropanol	2.0	1.125	-0.875	1.0	1.54	0.54
Hexafluoroacetone hydrate	6.80	7.50	0.70	1.6	2.00	0.4

* Values of log K and 'n' have been taken from the results of equilibrium studies¹

It is found that values of both f and r are positive and f is always greater than r, thus showing that alcohol molecules influence both forward and backward reaction but the influence on the former is greater. The unexpectedly high protonation power (measured by the association constant, K) of hexafluoroacetone hydrate is contributed at least partly by its high forward rate constant k_1 , while the low protonation power of trifluoroethanol is contributed at least by its somewhat high rate constant for reverse reaction. Although the forward rate constant for C₅-fluoroalcohol is low, its protonation power is greater than that of trifluoroethanol and comparable to C₇-fluoroalcohol. It may be that a very low value of rate constant for reverse reaction (that is, very high value of log k_{-1}) is responsible for this type of behaviour.

It has been discussed in our equilibrium studies¹ that trifluoroethanol exists in highly associated forms, while 2, 2-dinitropropanol exists predominantly in monomeric form. It is noted that the value of 'n' for 2, 2-dinitropropanol is unity, while for trifluoroethanol it is 3.8. Thus, the value of 'n' may be taken at least qualitatively as an index for the degree of autocomplexation of alcohol molecules.

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Calcutta—32.

Received August 24, 1968

8. R. N. Haszeldine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1757.

9. W. J. Middleton and R. V. Lindsey, Jr, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 4948.